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Evaluation of Microbial Population of Hydrocarbon Utilizing Microorganisms of Fluted pumpkin (*Telfaira occidentalis*) Rhizosphere and non-Rhizosphere Soils

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ABSTRACT

The rising cost and efficacy of the usual physicochemical remediation methods called for proffering alternative solution for *in-situ* application of remediation which rely on activities of microorganisms and rhizosphere plants (rhizoremediation). Comparative studies on its effectiveness with biostimulation techniques in remediation of crude oil contaminated soil are scarcely available. The study was undertaken to investigate the microbial populations, types of bacteria and fungi species present in the rhizosphere of edible crops in petroleum hydrocarbon polluted soil. To investigate this, contaminated and uncontaminated rhizosphere of plants species *Telfaira occidentalis* (Fluted pumpkin), were selected and screened in two locations (Umuechem 1 and Umuechem 2) in Rivers State, for rhizosphere effects and the presence of Total Heterotrophic bacteria (THB) and Fungi (TF), Hydrocarbon Utilizing bacteria (HUB) and fungi (HUF) populations. Soil dilution plate method on Nutrient agar (NA), Potato Dextrose agar (PDA) and Oil Mineral Salt agar (OMSA) was employed for the enumeration of these organisms. The four plants used for this study, which harbored higher populations of HUB and HUF were further subjected to tolerance test to the same level of crude oil contamination for fourteen weeks after planting (14WAP). The crude oil contaminated soil were further prepared and subjected to treatments with 2% and 6% level of organic manure in this manner: soil alone (S), Soil+oil (SO), Soil +oil +organic manure (SOOM) in two sets. One set, planted with the four most tolerance plants (P), Plant +oil (PS), Plant + soil+ oil (PSO), and Plant + soil +oil + organic manure (PSOOM). The other set unplanted, and served as control. Both sets were compared for as the study proceeded for fourteen weeks. After this, standard methods were adopted for the determination of microbiological and physicochemical characteristics; bacterial identification was carried out using colonial morphological and biochemical characteristics. Fungal identification was by macroscopic and microscopic examination of isolates. After this, THB, TF, HUB and HUF colony counts (CFU/g) were determined together with microbial population, diversity pattern, and residual total petroleum hydrocarbon, total organic carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus content were analysed. Evidence from the results has revealed that treatments with organic manure influenced the growth, populations, and types of THB, TF, HUB and HUF. The predominant bacterial genera were identified as *Bacillus* sp, *Micrococcus* sp, *Pseudomonas* sp, *Klebsiellasp*, *Enterobactersp*, *Alcaligenessp*, *Staphylococcus* sp, *Proteus* sp, *Flavobacteriasp*, *Corynebacteriasp*, *Strptococussp*, *Serratiasp*, *Norcardiasp*. Fungal isolates are *Aspergillus Niger*, *Candida* sp, *Trichodermasp*, *Penicillumsp*, *Mucorsp*, *Geotrichumsp*, *Fusariumsp*, *Rhizopussp*, *Chaetomiumsp*, and *Clasdosporiumsp*. There was a reduction in TPH, TOC, nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) as they were lost into the rhizosphere, because their concentration were higher in rhizosphere than in non- rhizosphere soils receiving the same treatments. ($P < 0.05$) Oil concentrations, organic manure, treatments and rhizosphere effects influenced the microbial community structure, diversity, types and their populations. Soil+oil+organic manure (SOOM) and plant + soil + oil +organic manure (PSOOM), recorded the highest reduction of TPH with time. Highest TPH reduction in rhizosphere of *Telfaira* sp, 78.4% and 86.1% as against unplanted soil of 70.4% and 59.4% respectively, from initial levels 28,600mg/kg and 7190 mg/kg contamination. Emphatically to say, that rhizoremediation and biostimulation has proved to be a better and effective techniques for cleanup of crude oil polluted soil environment in this study.

Keywords: Evaluation, Microbial Population, Hydrocarbon Utilizing, Microorganisms, Fluted pumpkin (*Telfaira occidentalis*) Rhizosphere, Soil.

INTRODUCTION

There has been growing public concern regarding the release of petroleum hydrocarbons into the environment. The nonchalant attitude by the multinational oil companies operating in Nigeria especially in the Niger Delta region has led to the problem of crude oil pollution of farmlands, causing serious problems to food safety. This is because, the persistence of oil pollution could result to the release of toxic pollutants into the food chain and water bodies thereby threatening the entire ecosystem (Nduka, 1985). Hence, our major concern is how to develop a robust sustainable environment as to enjoy a comfortable living today without jeopardising the prospect of our future generations from inheriting a worst environment. In other hand, how do we ensure environmental sustainability to be able to bequeath a robust and sound environment to future generation? This can be done when we realize the potential of biostimulation, a process of utilising a combination of cheap, environmentally friendly and widely available nutrients such as poultry droppings, cow dung, goat faeces and fish pond water to enhance microbial growth to ensure complete mineralization of the petroleum hydrocarbons in the soil environment. Thus, contributing to superb agronomic and environmental management as to promote healthy lifestyle in our nation and across the globe. This phenomenon is called rhizobacteria (PGPR) which are a plant growth promoting rhizobacteria which are a group of free living bacteria that colonize the rhizosphere and benefit from the root growth. Bacteria of different genera were identified as PGPR of which *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas sp* predominant (Ayedet *al.*, 2015). PGPR influence a direct control on plant growth by production of phytohormones, solubilization of inorganic phosphates, and increased iron uptake by iron chelating siderophores and volatile compounds that affect the plant hormonal response (Asadabadi&Saïen, 2016). Enhanced bioremediation (*ex-situ*) offers a cost – effective means of pollutants clean up and has been judged to be the best option, reliable tool for modelling and optimization of crude oil bioremediation techniques (Udotonget *al.*, 1997).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Samples for the Study

Rhizosphere and non Rhizosphere soil samples, crude oil (petroleum Hydrocarbon) polluted soil, Organic manure treatment on plant growth Four treatment; each of poultry droppings, cow dung, goat faeces and fish pond waste water and Control samples.

The study focused on their Microbiology- Bacteria and Fungi ,Total heterotrophic bacterial, total Coliform and fungal count, Hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial and hydrocarbon utilizing fungal count , Ratio and percentage (%) of HUB or HUF to THB or TFC.

Analysis of physicochemical properties of petroleum hydrocarbon polluted soils. And evaluation of the effects of organic manure treatment on plants growth. Four treatments : each of poultry droppings, cow dung, Goat faeces and fish pond waste water (water from the raring of *Clariasgarepeneus* with deposits of feeds , and faeces) were applied to the crude oil contaminated soil to serve as enrichment media for microbial growth.

Study Area

The study area was at Umuechem in Etche Local Government Area,(Rivers East Senatorial District) in Rivers State of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Unuechem is a community which is about six square kilometers in size (in-dwelling), accessible by land and about twenty kilometers to Okehi (Etche LGA headquarters) and thirty kilometers by road to Port Harcourt city Rivers State capital) respectively. Umuechem is in Otamiri oil fields of the Shell Petroleum Company of Nigeria Limited (SPDC) and harbors oil wells:Umuechem Well 15s flowline(4”Umuechem 15S Flowline of SPDC/Land East HUB, with coordinates spill points, Northing 5.00899, Easting, 7.02039 using measuring unit, WGS84. Other oil fields that SPDC operates in Umuechem are 8” Umuechem- Nkpoku Delivery Line, coordinates of spill points measured using the GPS readings N05⁰ 00’ 10.4”, E007⁰ 01’ 15.8”, Umuechem Well 9,Umuechem Flare site, Otamiri TNT Manifold flowline and Otamiri Well 5 flowline. The study area was selected based on the population density, industrial and commercial activities involving the use of diesel and kerosene for transportation, cooking and smoking of fish/meat.

Collection of Crude Oil Contaminated Soils

The soil samples were randomly collected at two different parts designated Umuechem 1, Umuechem 2 from non-crude oil contaminated area (control) at a depth of 0-15 cm with a clean soil auger into sterile polythene bags. The samples (about 300g each) were labelled and transported to the laboratory in a cooler packed with ice block for analysis.

Non-rhizosphere soils (i.e. soils from unpolluted rhizosphere at different points Umuechem I and Umuechem 2, were also collected at depth of 0-15cm about 5-10g of the soil was collected into a sterile polythene bag using a sterile hand trowel and allowed to air dry at ambient temperature.

Five replicate samples of rhizosphere from each plant species and non-rhizosphere soils collected randomly within each of the sampling areas were pooled together and taken straight for microbiological and physicochemical analysis after thorough mixing. Analysis of collected field samples were performed within 24 hours of sampling from field to laboratory.

Processing of Samples

The soil samples were processed using the method of Almansoori *et al.*, (2005). Ten gram of the soil samples were weighed and added to 90ml of sterile distilled water to get an aliquot. One millilitre (1ml) of the aliquots, were then serially diluted using the ten-fold serial dilution method as described by Barbaet *al.*, (2012).

Microbiological Analysis of Petroleum Hydrocarbon Polluted Soil

Media Used

Nutrient agar (NA) was used for the isolation of (THB), the medium was prepared in accordance with the Titan Biotech LTD specifications (i.e. the manufacturer). Twenty eight (28g) grams of the nutrient agar (NA) powder was dissolved in 1 litre of de-ionized water of 1.0 litres and sterilized for 15.0 minutes at 121.0°C for 15 Psi in an autoclave. It was allowed to cool to 45°C, thereafter, the medium was dispensed into Petri dishes to allow for solidification in a sterile condition. Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) was prepared according to the manufacturers specifications. Thirty-eight (38g) grams of PDA powder was dissolved in 1 litre de-ionized water and sterilized for 15.0 minutes at 121°C, 15.0 Psi in an autoclave. After cooling to 45°C, a tetracycline antibiotic (2drops) was introduced into molten PDA to prevent the growth of bacteria. This was homogenized thoroughly under aseptic condition (Walker and Cowell, 1976), Harrigan and McCance, 1990; Paul and Clark (2008). After which, the medium was dispensed into petridishes to allow for solidification under sterile condition.

Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria (HUB) and Fungi (HUF) were isolated and enumerated on oil mineral salt agar (OMSA) as described by Mills *et al.*, (1978) and adapted by Obireetal., (2008), Okpokwasili and Nwogu (2011). The constituents of the (OMSA) include agar 20g, de-ionized water IL. Na₂ HPO₄, 1.25g, NaCl 15g, KH₂PO₄, 0.83g, KCl, 0.29g, MgSO₄, 7. H₂O, 0.42g, NaNO₃, 0.42g and pH 7.13, (approx). This was autoclaved as earlier described. Thereafter, filter-sterilized crude oil from Millipore filter of pore size 0.22um (Obire, 1988) was introduced into the above constituents at 1% v/v after cooling to temperature of 45°C, homogenized. And the medium was dispensed into Petri-dishes to allow for solidification while maintaining sterile condition with addition of antibiotics tetracycline (1drop) to fungi plates to inhibit the growth of bacteria.

Microbial Identification

The bacterial isolates were identified by the conventional microbiological methods such as Gram Staining and Biochemical reactions. They were characterized by colonial/cellular morphology, Gram stain reaction, motility, and biochemical tests. The organisms were identified based on the standard key of Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology and reference to ABIS online identification tool for bacteria.

Enumeration of Total Fungi

Potato dextrose agar (PDA) was used for the isolation and enumeration of total heterotrophic fungi. The medium was prepared as specified by the manufacturer and aseptically dispensed into sterile petri dishes and allowed to solidify at room temperature. The solidified dry medium was then inoculated after performing serial ten-fold dilution. The culture plates were all incubated for 72 hours at room temperature. After incubation, growth was observed and colonies counted in the triplicate plates. The

colony forming units per gram of rhizosphere sample were calculated from the mean counts of the triplicate plates.

Purification of Bacteria Isolates

Once the total heterotrophic bacteria were counted, culture plates from each sample were selected for purification. Based on cultural characteristics, the colonies were picked, labeled and transferred to fresh sterile nutrient agar plates and incubated for 24 hours at room temperature. After incubation, the isolates were all gram stained and viewed under the oil immersion objective (x100) of a compound microscope. Mixed cultures were further sub-cultured to obtain a pure culture.

Analysis of Plant Samples for Physicochemical Parameters

The different parts of the plant, leaves, stems and roots were weighted separately using a weighing balance, Mettler AE 163 for fresh weight. After this, the plant parts were placed in a desiccator before readings were taken for the dry weight. The dried portions of the plant parts were ashed and the powder dissolved in distilled water and digested with acid for various forms of analysis.

Collection and Pre-Treatment of Plant Samples

Samples of plant Cowpea (*Telfaira occidentalis*), were collected in triplicates. Labeled and placed in a clean contaminant free polythene bags in which they were conveyed to the laboratory. Thereafter, they were thoroughly washed in tap water and rinsed three times with distilled water to remove all traces of sand. The plants were then separated into leaf, stem and root using a clean stainless steel knife and placed separately in well-labelled porcelain dishes. The samples were then dried in Fisher Econotemp electric oven model 55G maintained at 105°C and allowed to dry overnight to constant weight (Ekekwe, 1981).

Evaluation of the Effects of Organic Manure Treatment on Plant Growth

Treatments and Collection of Organic Manure Samples

Four treatments; each of poultry droppings, cow dung, Goat faeces and fish pond waste water (water gotten from the rearing of *Claria sgariepeus* with deposits of feeds, and faeces), were applied to the crude oil contaminated soil (COCS) to serve as enrichment media for the microbial growth on the Crude Oil Contaminated Soil (COCS).

The poultry droppings and cowdung were collected from the poultry farm and abattoir belonging to the Faculty of Agriculture of Rivers State University. The Goat faeces (GF) were collected from the Mile 3 Goat Market behind the park whilst Fish pond waste water was supplied to me by Mr. Barine Rogers of Animal and Environmental Biology Department of the Rivers State University, who operates a fish farming business within the University. All these treatments samples were sent to laboratory and were homogenized, composited separately before use (Obire *et al.*, 2008).

Pre-Planting Preparation and Plant Viability Testing

The seeds of Cowpea, were tested for their viability to grow on crude oil contaminated soil. The seeds were first soaked in water, and later removed those that floated in water were discarded while submerged viable seeds were selected for propagation. After this, a volume of 3kg of Crude Oil Contaminated Soil were weighed and introduced into each of the five bags making up to twenty (20) bags with surface area of 442cm and allowed to stand for two weeks. The bags were labelled as PSPD, PSGF, PSCD and PSFPW and watered to 75% field moisture capacity. Four to six Cowpea, seeds were introduced into each bag to a depth of 1.2cm and left to germinate. The experiment was laid down in a completely, randomized block designed with planting distance of 75 x 143cm² in three replicates. The plants were observed for a period of 14-30 days. At the expiration of 30 days, it was expected that the plants' seeds should start sprouting. The following were determined:

- a) Leave area, % germination, stem girth, and plant height. The formula for calculating the percentage germination is given below:
 - i) **Percentage (%) germination** =
$$\frac{\text{Number of seedlings that germinated per pot}}{\text{Number of seeds planted per pot}} \times \frac{100}{1} \text{ (15)}$$
 - ii) **Leave Area:** The measurement of leave area. The method of Pearce *et al.*, (1995) was used. This is done by plotting the perimeter of the leaf against length x breath measurements.

The slope obtained from this was subsequently used as multiplying factor for length x breadth measurement.

(iii) **Stems Girth:** Stem girth was determined by using a Vernier Calliper and readings were recorded for each of the plants (Fluted pumpkin), that germinated from the various crude oil polluted soil and amended plots.

(v) **Plant Height Measurement:** The plant height was done with the help of meter rule, the plant height was determined at the early growth stage and later at advanced stages i.e. mature stage, when the plants had outgrown the meter 4 weeks after planting and continued every 4 weeks for 12-16 weeks.

RESULTS

Results of Microbiological Analysis of Petroleum Hydrocarbon Polluted Soil

Bacterial and Fungal Populations Utilising Hydrocarbon in the Rhizosphere (Uncontaminated) of the Plants *Telfaira occidentalis* Used in Umuechem and Odagwa

Results of Rhizosphere Total Culturable Heterotrophs and Hydrocarbon Utilisers in Umuechem 1 and Umuechem 2

The results revealed that rhizosphere soils harboured total culturable heterotrophs bacterial population of 10^6 CFU/g irrespective of plant; total cultural rhizosphere fungal population were found to be highly distinct, thus, ranging from 10^5 to 10^6 CFU/g among the plants species in both environments. Similarly, the bulk soil from both environments also harbored heterotrophs bacteria and fungi counts which range from 10^5 to 10^6 CFU/g of soil. The rhizosphere heterotrophic bacterial population and hydrocarbon utilizers differed significantly among plant species ($P < 0.05$) in both location. In the *Telfaira occidentalis* rhizosphere its total heterotrophic bacterial population were found to be higher than fungi at $P < 0.5$, except, where fungal and bacterial populations were not significantly, statistically different at $P < 0.05$.

Similarly, heterotrophic bacterial population in the rhizosphere for each plant species in cow dung nutrients were found to be higher than fungal except for fish pond waste water, which showed higher counts of total fungi over bacterial counts. However, the differences between the heterotrophic bacterial and fungal counts were significantly statistically different only in the rhizosphere of *Fluted pumpkin* ($P < 0.05$). The total bulk soil (i.e. soil away from root zone effect), population of culturable bacterial heterotrophs and hydrocarbon utilizers from the two study locations were found to be higher in Umuechem 1 and Umuechem 2. On the other hand, while the total fungal counts in the bulk soil from the two study locations in the Umuechem 1 & 2, were found to be five folds higher than the crude oil contaminated rhizosphere soil ($P < 0.05$). The rhizosphere of all the replicate plant species screened revealed significantly a higher total counts of hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria than fungi ($P < 0.05$) (Figure. 4.3 & 4.4). The bacterial counts of hydrocarbon utilizers were two or more fold higher than their corresponding hydrocarbon utilizing fungal counts in both environments. *Telfaira occidentalis* had, bacterial counts of hydrocarbon utilizers that were higher than its corresponding hydrocarbon utilizing fungal counts. The plants species, screened, *Telfaira occidentalis* harboured the highest total hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial and fungal populations $2.20 \times 10^6 \pm 9.413$ CFU/g and $1.12 \times 10^7 \pm 2.564$ CFU/g in the rhizosphere while non rhizosphere recorded the lowest population of hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria $1.2 \times 10^5 \pm 3.457$ CFU/g and fungi $6.9 \times 10^3 \pm 2.085$ CFU/g and fungi $2.0 \times 10^3 \pm 2.612$ CFU/g in its rhizosphere. *Telfaira occidentalis* from 2% and 6% concentration of organic manure had the highest bacterial counts of $2.4 \times 10^5 \pm 2.517$ CFU/g and fungal counts $7.0 \times 10^4 \pm 1.413$ CFU/g population of hydrocarbon utilizers in the rhizosphere respectively. The non rhizosphere in the other hand, harboured the lowest counts of hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria ($1.6 \times 10^4 \pm 1.472$ CFU/g) and fungi ($2.4 \times 10^3 \pm 2.086$ CFU/g) respectively.

Results of Rhizosphere Percentage Culturable Population of Hydrocarbon Utilizers in the Umuechem and Odagwa

The assessment of rhizosphere Cowpea (Fluted punpkin) on the bases of its percentage (%) frequency of occurrence of (HUB) and (HUF) revealed that more than 10% of their total heterotrophic bacterial population were hydrocarbon utilizers in the following order bacillus FROM rhizosphere (38.5%), non rhizosphere (27.8%), Arthrobacter from the rhizosphere had percentage occurrence as (33.4%) and its non rhizosphere was (20.3%),while proteus and Ewina had less than 25%. Therhizosphere fungal population of hydrocarbon utilizers as *isolated from Telfaira occidentalis are follows Aspergillus*, (48.9%), penicilliumsp(35.4%), *Saccharomyces and candidasp* had above (30.4%) *pichiasp*, (15.85%), Daboromyces 28.5%, Torulopsis had 18.9% and cladosporium had up to 33.2% . The non rhizosphere had its hydrocarbon utilizers as 14.7% and 15.6% respectively. The organisms identified were mostly Gram positive and Gram negative rods with few Gram positive cocci. These organisms were: bacillus, Escherichia coli, corynebacterium, micrococcus, staphylococcus, Artrobacter,Flavobacterium, Cromobacterium, AlcaligenesSp, Pseudomonas Sp,Aeromonas,Acinobacter, Ewinia and proteus. The fungal isolates include: Cladosporium, *Fusarium Aspergillus, Mucor Rhizopus and Monilia, Penicellium* others were Pichia *Torulopsis, Saccharomyces and Debaromyces Sp Candida Sp*.

Fig.1: Total Culturable Heterotrophic Rhizosphere and bulk soil bacteria and fungal counts (CFU/g) in the Crude oil contaminated soil

Fig. 2: Ratio of Total Heterotrophic Fungi to Hydrocarbon Utilizing Fungi Count for Fluted pumpkin (*Telfaira occidentalis*)

Fig 3: Ratio of Total Heterotrophic Bacteria Counts to Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria counts during the experiment for Fluted pumpkin (*Telfaira occidentalis*)

The Ratio of Total Heterotrophic Bacteria Counts to Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria counts and total fungi and hydrocarbon utilizing fungi counts are presented in Fig.1 and Fig 2. From the results of ratio of total heterotrophic bacteria to hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria counts obtained during the course of the study are as follows: in the treatment with poultry droppings (PD) the ratio of THB:HUB of the crude contaminated soil amended with poultry droppings was 18. In cow dung treatment the ratio of THB/HUB was 16 and in goat faeces (GF) the ratio of THB/HUB was 1.5 while the THF /HUF ratio recorded for fish pond waste water (FPWW) treatment was 3.5. The Ratio for the unamended experimental set up had its THB/HUB ratio as 1.5 and THF/ HUF ratio was 4.8 respectively.

Fig. 4: The girth, leaf area and height growth of *Telfaira occidentalis* at various treatments with organic manure monitored (days in weeks).

On organic manure treatment on microbial growth, the following results were obtained, there was changes in microbial population of the different physiological groups during the treatment of crude oil contaminated soil planted with Fluted pumpkin. with the treatment amendment poultry dropping (PD) cow during (CD) Goat Faeces (GF) and fish pond waste water(FPWW) Treatment amended with poultry droppings, there was progressive increase in THBC from 1.93×10^3 cfCFU/g subsequently, a decrease on THB counts with COCS rhizosphere soil from 4.25×10^5 CFU/g in week 2 to 1.35×10^3 in week 4. Likewise, the HUB counts had from 2.70×10^4 CFU/g at the initial starting of the experiment to 5.10×10^7 CFU/g in week 2 to 1.38×10^5 by the 4th week. The THF and HUF counts CFU/g from 1.53×10^5 and 1.24×10^3 to 2.5×10^3 to 3.8×10^3 CFU/g by week 4 was a reduction in THF and HUF counts to 1.6×10^3 to 1.2×10^2 CFU/g.

DISCUSSION

Discussions on the Microbiological Analysis of Petroleum Hydrocarbon Polluted Soil Rhizosphere Total Culturable Heterotrophs and Hydrocarbon Utilisers

The microbial density of plant roots otherwise known as the rhizosphere was investigated. In this research, four rhizosphere samples were analysed and two other non-rhizosphere soil samples were analysed and used as control. Results from this study revealed the microbial community of bacteria and fungi in the rhizosphere and non-rhizosphere, which counts ranges from 10^5 to 10^7 CFU/g of soil. These counts are in agreement with the earlier works of Ochchukwu(2013), who reported that, a particular microbial counts around 1.5cm top layer of soil contains up to 10^7 to 10^9 CFU/g. The culturable fungal count of a rhizosphere species (propagules) were reported to have been around 10^6 CFU/g (Odu, *et al.*, 1985). In earlier work of Odokuma *et al.*, (2003) the value of microbial counts were within the range of 10^5 to 10^6 taken from a single fraction of 1g of soil for both bacteria and fungi. Yeates and Darrah (2019), revealed that rhizosphere of *Heveabrsiliensis* had colony counts of 10^7 and 10^4 CFU/g of soil for heterotrophic bacteria and total fungi respectively. Whilst Odu and Mclvor (1990) reported counts ranging from 10^6 to 10^7 CFU/g of soil for bacteria alone in rhizosphere of *Amaranthushybridus*.

The presence of petroleum hydrocarbon pollution in the environment alters the microbial populations and its diversity pattern. It also leads to increase in microbial activity and total microbial counts. Atlas (1983) reported that soil polluted with crude oil at a percentage above 39% harbours the highest number of microorganisms. Obire and Anyanwu (2008) asserted that total heterotrophic fungal counts (THFC)

increased in days under crude oil contaminated soil. The result obtained from this study, is therefore, in agreement with the reports of Okoh(2006), who stated that rhizosphere region is a highly favourable habitat for the proliferation and metabolism of numerous microbial types. The report went further to state that the rhizosphere flora has greater ability to effect rapid biochemical changes than the organism of fallow soil. The rhizosphere is region of highest microbial population than the region of soil devoid of plants root. This is because root exudates, sugars, amino acids, hormones, vitamins and shedline decomposition of root cells and tissues, promote the growth of bacteria and fungi (Osilon&Fletcher, 2000).

This studies on microorganism associated with the rhizosphere of edible crops in petroleum hydrocarbon polluted soils from the oil producing areas in Rivers State, showed that isolation of yeasts and moulds (*Candida Lypolytica*, *Trichoderma*, *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* sp, agreed with earlier work of Obire (1988), who also isolated same organisms and asserted that these organisms offer best oil degraders in oil polluted environment. Okpokwasili and Nworgu(2011) reported counts within a value of 10^5 to 10^6 CFU/g soil from 1g of non-stressed soil for bacteria and fungi. Obire and Anyanwu (2008); Obire and Amusan (2013); Obire and Akinde (2006); Jaja and Obire (2015); reported colonial counts of microorganisms isolated from soil contaminated with petroleum hydrocarbon within range of 10^6 to 10^7 and 10^5 to 10^6 . In this study, there is a slight variation in the heterotrophic bacterial and total fungal counts as was previously recorded, either due to complex nature of soil, study area, sample and period of sampling and isolation.

There is not much significant difference among the plant species in terms of populations of THB, HUB, TF and HUF in the rhizosphere. This could be attributed to the fact that the study centred on one location within the rain forest zone with reoccurrence of long term crude oil spillage on the environment not treated nor remediated. This finding is in agreement with Obire (1988), who reported that microbial composition around plants roots (rhizosphere) are largely influenced by root exudates. Exudates by roots are related to species genus and age of plants and habitat (Oyeyiola, 2010).

The isolation of notable soil microorganism especially fungal isolates such as *Candida lypolytica*, *Fusarium*, and *Clasdosporium* species, and bacterial species *Pseudomonas putida*, are principal agents of petroleum degraders in soil (Atlas, 1981). The heterotrophic bacterial populations in the rhizosphere indicated progressively higher than their corresponding fungal population out of the four plants species studied. This is in line with the previous work of Oyeyiola et al., (2013) who reported that bacteria are known to be consistently higher in number than fungi in a typical garden soil. Although, fungi tends to predominate in acidic soils (Oyeyiola, 2010). It is not surprising to report that, the large number of total fungi present in the rhizosphere of some of the plants may be accounted for by the acidic pH of the soil within the study area.

From the non- rhizosphere soils, the heterotrophic and hydrocarbon utilizing bacterial and fungal populations from Umuechem 1 were higher than those from Umuechem 2. This could be because the heterogeneous microbiota of most non-contaminated soil are composed of naturally occurring hydrocarbon degrading microorganisms such that petroleum spillage into the soil could preferentially encourage proliferations of that component parts of microbial community capable of adjusting and utilizing the freshly introduced oil components as source of carbon and energy (Atlas, 1983).

Discussion of Plant Girth, Leaf Area and Height Growth under various Crude Oil Concentrations in the Soil

The plant height increased overtime as a result of the soil amendment with the various organic manure additions. The control treatment had the highest plant height than the other treatments with the organic manure. Treatments with poultry droppings at 6% had the highest plant height this is followed by treatments with cow dung, the least plant height was observed in treatment of goat faeces and fish pond water especially at 2%. By this observation, it can be concluded that the soil amendments with organic nutrients encouraged a rise in the height of the various plants with time in weeks. Though it is possible to say that, without organic manure treatments, plants can hardly grow, survive and increase or maintain height under the various concentration of crude oil contamination in the soil, because of toxicity effects of

these hydrocarbon components on the plants growth. Meaning that, some plants in unpolluted soil without treatments had recorded highest value for plant height. This indicates that unpolluted soil remains the best option for increased plant height (Oghoet *al.*, 2009). The role played by microorganisms in the breakdown of hydrocarbon, complemented the plants in their competition for nutrients and oxygen which are usually limited in soil. The microbes, creates an anaerobic condition resulting from oxygen depletion and of course, this triggers the evolution by microbes of hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) which are phytotoxic to plants. The presence of crude oil in the soil, reduces aeration and moisture content and this affects the physical structure of the soil (Abbas *et al.*, 2013). The ability of *Telfaira occidentalis* (Fluted pumpkin) to maintain resilience to crude oil contamination, is one of the many features of phyto remediation, others include: hardness, competitiveness, production of large biomass and high growth rate as well as pollution tolerance (Bashan, *et al.*, 2005). Bashan, (1988) had reported that increased concentration of crude oil to soil meant for agricultural planting of crops, usually will cause decreases in stem and leaf area. Omosun *et al.*, (2008) reported of a plant *Saccharum officinarum* tested under different level of crude oil concentration, the plants exhibited decrease in response to the crude oil pollution. He asserted that the effects were significantly evident on the leaf area and stem girth of *Saccharum officinarum* in similar studies. Omosun (2008) reported an increase of growth in root length of *Cymbopogon ambiguus* in diesel oil contaminated soil compared to the uncontaminated soil. He also maintained that *Brachiaria decumbens*, at 0.5 and 1.0% w/w, had no significant difference between the contaminated and non-contaminated soil (0.0% w/w) at 9-12 weeks. This work supported my finding that the stem girth of *Telfaira occidentalis* observed no significant difference in their stem girths in the soils treated with cowdung, poultry droppings, goat faeces and fish pond water after 12 weeks observation. Shown a decrease with increase depth of soil. Soil aeration is reduced affecting available oxygen diffusion into the soil for effective biodegradation, occurring within 30.0cm of soil in vertical profile (Okolo, 2001). This finding gave a pass mark to *Telfaira occidentalis* (Fluted pumpkin) whose root length measurements were farther than 30cm into the soil the contaminated rhizosphere soil amended with organic nutrients. Its root structure and luxurious large surface area which provided robust rhizosphere for efficient invasion of associated microorganisms was enough reason for its selection. Ogbo *et al.*, (2009), reported that oxygen and nitrogen which are important nutrients for plants growth are disrupted and unavailable in soil when there is oil spillage to the environment, as a result, nutrients addition to contaminated soil should be encouraged and incorporated into the soil by tilling in order to improve soil aeration and fertility (April and Sims, 1990).

Discussion of Root Lengths and Plant Weights (Dry and Fresh) under various Concentration of Organic Nutrients

There are copious materials regarding effects of crude oil on the fresh and dry weight of some plants, while Muratova, (2007), Ogbo *et al.*, (2009), Parke *et al.*, (1990) and Omosun *et al.*, (2008) reported tremendous decrease in plant biomass with an increase in the level of oil in the soil, a level up to 0.60% w/w concentration.

Merki *et al.*, (2000), on the other hand, reported increase in biomass at oil concentration of 5.0% w/w. Also, Oyeyiola *et al.*, (2005) reported increase in plant biomass at crude oil concentrations of 1.0% w/w. There is slight difference in my findings regarding the fresh and dry weights of plants used for this study. The results for the fresh and dry weight of *Telfaira occidentalis* (Fluted pumpkin) showed high values in fresh and dry weight in treatment with various organic manure. The fresh and dry weight did not show any significant difference with those of uncontaminated soil in *Telfaira occidentalis* (Fluted pumpkin) that recorded decrease fresh and dry weight at 2% organic manure, but suddenly, increased when the concentration of treatment increased up to 6% w/w for 12 weeks. This increase in biomass witnessed at high levels of organic manure treatments, could suggest that, high crude oil concentrations, above certain percentage of organic manure treatments would caused a reduction in the plant biomass. Low level of crude oil concentration in soil 0.5% w/w to 1.0% w/w may produce growth stimulating effects on plants leading to increased crop yield (Barba, *et al.*, 2012). This is because petroleum hydrocarbon may act as co-factor in growth stimulating hormones (Barca, 2005). The decrease or increase in fresh and dry weight

of plant is dependent on the species of plant, level of crude oil concentration in the soil and organic nutrients treatments.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In Nigeria, especially in Niger Delta, there is a dearth of information on the role of microbial community associated with plants rhizosphere with respect to edible plant species. Having noted this, there is need therefore to conduct research of microbial community of rhizosphere plants in petroleum hydrocarbon contaminated soil. This has been achieved by the isolation and identification of heterotrophs and hydrocarbon utilizing microbes, bacteria and fungi associated with the rhizosphere of locally sourced edible crops. The high population of hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria and fungi in the soil around the rhizosphere plants used in the study suggest that the hydrocarbon utilizers were adapted to the quantity of hydrocarbons in the environment and thereby increased their proliferation in the polluted area. The study also reveals that most of the organisms isolated, Total heterotrophic bacterial, Total heterotrophic fungi were part of the utilizers. The response of these microorganisms in the soil contaminated environments suggest that the isolated bacteria and fungi could have utilized the oil as source of carbon and energy, indicating that they can be better and effectively used for cleanup of the crude oil contaminated soils.

RECOMMENDATION

Quantitative screening of plants studies need to be developed to identify the exact and capable plants that can tolerate high crude oil contamination. Also, agricultural crude oil contaminated soils within oil bearing communities can be cleaned in a short period of time through combined effects of rhizoremediation and biostimulation techniques. The study revealed that microorganisms maintained major key players in the decontamination of petroleum hydrocarbon polluted lands and rid the environment of many of these compounds that pollute the environment. Niger Delta is the base of oil exploration and exploitation, which led to incessant oil spillage that pollutes the environment, hence, alternative remediation techniques are advocated especially technology that can utilize nature capacity of plants and microorganisms to clean up the oil contaminated environment.

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